

STUDY OF ECOCENTRIC APTITUDE OF UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS TO FIND SOLUTIONS TO ENVIRONMENTAL ISSUES

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Abstract

The need for ecocentric thinking among young people, especially undergraduate students who will be the next generation of leaders, professionals and responsible citizens, has been highlighted by the growing environmental crises of this century. Current study examines undergraduate students' ecocentric aptitude, which is the capacity and tendency to put ecological values ahead of anthropocentric interests, in relation to environmental issues. The research explores students' attitudes, awareness, and proactive behaviors toward sustainability through a mixed-method approach involving surveys and interviews. The results show that undergraduates have a moderate to high level of environmental concern, but there is a disconnect between ecological awareness and practical action. This is where academic institutions can play a key role in creating environmentally conscious citizens.

Introduction

Global warming, climatic changes, environmental degradation, habitat loss and extinction of species have emerged as serious global issues that warrant urgent attention. The youth, more specifically the undergraduate students, through their education, abilities, technology, creativity and social influence can bring about the necessary environmental changes. Education influenced ecocentric behavior of the youth is hence important. (Naess, 1989)

Ecocentrism is a philosophy that places the well-being of ecosystems and the environment above human interest. It is in contrast to anthropocentrism, where the human interest are given the utmost importance. Ecocentrism views humans as one part of a larger ecological community, recognizing intrinsic value in all living organisms and natural processes regardless

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of their usefulness to humans. It recognizes that every living organism has an intrinsic value and can rightfully use the natural resources beyond their use to humanity. (BARTON, 1994)

The objective of the present study was to judge the ecocentric aptitude of undergraduate students and assess how this disposition translates into practical efforts to mitigate environmental challenges. The research also examines the role of educational institutions in cultivating ecocentric values among students. (VANISHREE SAH, 2024)

Literature Review

According to Arne Naess's (1973) Ecocentric environmental ethic, nature has inherent value that goes beyond human utility. The anthropocentric worldview, on the other hand, views nature primarily as a resource for human use. According to research, ecocentric people engage in more pro-environmental practices, such as recycling, energy conservation, and sustainable consumption. (P.Wesley Schultz, 2004)

According to research on environmental education, behavior change is not always ensured by knowledge alone. (Anja Kollmuss, 2002) Rather, community involvement, personal ethics, and emotional engagement are better indicators of environmental action. Green curricula and sustainability initiatives at academic institutions have been associated with higher levels of behavioral engagement and ecological literacy. (Lozano, 2013)

The aptitude component—students' ability and willingness to use ecocentric thinking to solve environmental problems—has, however, received little attention in the literature. By examining the cognitive (knowledge) and affective (attitude) components of ecocentric aptitude, this study makes an effort to close the gap.

Methodology

This study is based on primary data collected through questionnaire. Structured sampling method was employed. The teachers in the Colleges were approached to administer the online questionnaire to the students. The teachers were requested to guide students if they face any difficulty in giving responses. Five-point Likert-type scale was used to examine environmental consciousness among the students. The scales were rated ranging from 1 to 5 as follows: 1 = completely disagree; 2 = somewhat disagree; 3 = Neutral; 4 = somewhat agree; 5 = fully agree. Measures of central tendency such as the arithmetic mean and standard deviation were used to summarize the perception of the students on their responsibilities towards the environment. Students' t-test was administered to show the extent of relationship between the attributes of anthropocentrism and ecocentrism. (Furkan BALTACI, 2015)

5. Results and Discussion

Male respondents were 44% and the remaining 56% female. The participants were recorded to be in the age group of 18-21 years. Among them 67% were 18 years of age, 22% in 19 years, 6% in 20 years and remaining in more than 21 years of age. Hence the sample predominantly belonged to undergraduate students.

Sr.	Questions	Yes %	No %
	Whether activities related to environment are carried out in your institution?	76	24
2	Do you take part in activities related to environment organized by your institution or others?	57	43
3	Do you study any courses related to environment?	61	39
4	Do you read any articles, research papers or watch TV shows, podcasts, videos, etc. related to environmental topics?	62	38
5	Do you take part in environmental campaigns?		

As mentioned in the table above, more than 76% of the respondents stated that activities related to environmental awareness, conservation and social actions are undertaken in their institution where they are studying while 57% of them replied that they do participate in such activities undertaken in their institution. 61% of the students replied that they study courses related to environment and 62% of them mentioned that they read articles, research papers or watch TV shows, podcasts, videos, etc. related to environmental topics. The institutions conduct activities like tree plantation, beach clean-up, awareness campaigns, waste management and many more. 28% of the respondents mentioned that they are physically involved in participating in activities related to environmental conservation while 24% of them said that they wish to participate in such activities in future. This concludes that majority of the student respondents are conscious regarding their environment they are living in and are doing their small part, in which ever way possible to preserve it.

The findings revealed that:

- 27% of respondents demonstrated a high level of environmental concern.
- 34% actively participated either physically or supported financially in environment related activities (e.g., tree plantation, beach clean-ups, campus clean-ups, awareness rallies, waste segregation and management).

ECOCENTRIC ATTRIBUTES			
Sr.	Propositions	Mean	SD
1.	Human population explosion is rapidly overtaking natural resource availability of the world.	4.01	1.16
2.	Human intervention with nature often causes calamities.	3.75	1.27
3.	Humans extensively use the natural resources without caring about their limited availability.	4.13	1.04
4.	Natural forces often over-power human's intelligence.	3.86	1.18
5.	Natural systems are very delicate and fragile.	3.75	1.19
6.	If the present pattern of use of natural resources is not changed, the humanity may face much more devastating environmental problems in future.	3.95	1.29
7.	Humans must appreciate the intrinsic value of nature without considering its use to humanity.	3.90	1.27
8.	It is very disheartening to see the environment getting destroyed for human's unplanned development.	3.89	1.29
9.	Sometimes the plants and animals seem to be behaving better than humans in environmental conservation.	4.13	1.24
ANTHROPOCENTRIC ATTRIBUTES			
10.	Humans have the right to alter the natural environment as per his needs.	2.75	1.45
11.	Humans will use their intelligence and creativity to make the world suitable to live despite of environmental problems.	3.58	1.24
12.	The environmental problems like climate change, deforestation, extinction of species, pollution and many more are often exaggerated.	3.34	1.27
13.	Since humans have high IQ level, they have the right to dominate nature.	2.43	1.35
14.	Humans will one day completely learn the mechanism behind all the environmental issues so that those can be solved permanently.	3.47	1.18
15.	Everything in the environment is valuable as it benefits humans.	3.89	1.33

In the questionnaire, two dimensions were obtained. These dimensions were named as 'Anthropocentric Attributes' and 'Ecocentric Attributes'. The mean of student respondent's Ecocentric attributes is 3.93 while the mean of Anthropocentric Attribute is 3.24. The numbers reveal that the students are more inclined towards ecocentric attributes than anthropocentric attributes. The perspectives attracting very high level of anthropocentric behaviour are 'Everything in the environment is valuable as it benefits humans', 'Humans will use their intelligence and creativity to make the world suitable to live despite of environmental problems' and 'Humans will one day completely learn the mechanism behind all the environmental issues so that those can be solved permanently'.

The anthropocentric attributes were tested between male and female respondents' using unpaired t test. The t value for standard deviation of 1.39 and standard error of 0.01 was calculated to be 8.85 greater than table value of 1.96 at $p = 0.05$ and $df = 496$. Hence, male

students were found to be more anthropocentric than females. This coincides with the eco-feminism ethics. It emphasizes on the profound connections of women to her environment. These results align with previous studies emphasizing that environmental education should move beyond cognitive understanding to experiential and value-based learning (Tilbury, 1995).

Conclusion

According to the study's findings, undergraduate students have a promising degree of ecocentric aptitude, but in order to convert this aptitude into meaningful environmental action, they need institutional and societal support. Universities ought to encourage student-led environmental projects, incorporate sustainability into all subject areas, and offer venues for hands-on ecological engagement.

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